

Comparative analysis of collocations of the Spanish verb echar in the learner corpora
CEDEL2 and CAES: errors and L1 influence

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Phraseology is known to be a problematic domain for learners of foreign languages (Mendizábal de la Cruz and Sastre Ruano, 2017); nevertheless, it constitutes an important area of language as it links it to the target culture (Castillo Carballo, 2003). The problems that might arise in the process of acquiring phraseological units concern their recognition and subsequent use in a pragmatically appropriate way: at the latter phase, in particular, errors of interlinguistic nature might arise (Orol González and Alonso Ramos, 2013). Against this background, this poster aims to investigate the use of phraseological units based on the Spanish verb echar (Martín Salcedo, 2015) in an analysis comparing its occurrences in two Learner Corpora: CEDEL2 and CAES. In particular, it aims to determine whether and to what extent L1 affects the acquisition of this verb and the level of the CEFR at which verbal phraseological units in which the verb echar appears are acquired. This is followed by a brief analysis of the phraseological errors related to this verb (Pérez Serrano, 2014). Regarding the frequency of errors, a substantial decrease in intermediate levels of language proficiency was hypothesized. As for interlinguistic influence, examples related to two L1s, namely English and Italian, have been analyzed. In this regard, a lower frequency of errors was expected in the Italian-Spanish interlanguage due to the proximity between the two languages (Bailini, 2016). The possible applications of this study concern the development of targeted and specific teaching activities for each level of language proficiency (Timofeeva Timofeev, 2013; Mendizábal de la Cruz and Sastre Ruano, 2017; Peramos Soler et al., 2010) to foster the acquisition of the phraseological units containing echar.

References

Orol González A., Alonso Ramos M. (2013) A Comparative Study of Collocations in a Native Corpus and a Learner Corpus of Spanish, in *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Volume 95, Pages 563-570, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.10.683>.

Martín Salcedo, J. (2015), *Échale ganas que te echamos una mano. Fraseología con el verbo echar*, in V CONGRESSO NORDESTINO DE PROFESSORES DE ESPANHOL, 2014, Teresina, Anais do V Congresso Nordestino de Profesores de Espanhol, Brasília: Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y Deporte.

Castillo Carballo, M. A. (2002), *Conocimiento cultural en la adquisición de la L2: la fraseología*, in *El Español, Lengua del Mestizaje y la Interculturalidad*, Actas del XIII Congreso Internacional de la ASELE, Murcia.

Bailini, S. (2016), *La interlengua de lenguas afines: el español de los italianos, el italiano de los españoles*, Milano: Led Edizioni.

Mendizábal de la Cruz, N., Sastre Ruano, M. Á. (2017), Problemas de las unidades fraseológicas verbales y su aplicación a la enseñanza del español como lengua extranjera, in Palabras Vocabulario Léxico: La lexicología aplicada a la didáctica y a la diacronía, Florencio del Barrio de la Rosa, Pages 49-62.

Pérez Serrano, M. (2014), Análisis de errores colocacionales en un corpus de aprendientes de ELE, in marcoELE. Revista de Didáctica Español Lengua Extranjera, 19 (2014), Redalyc, <https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=92152427011>

Timofeeva Timofeev, L. (2013), La fraseología en la clase de lengua extranjera: ¿misión imposible?, in Onomázein, 28, december, Pages 320-336, Santiago, Chile: Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile.

Peramos Soler, N., Leontaridi, E. & Ruiz Morales, M. (2009), Las unidades fraseológicas del español: su enseñanza y adquisición en la clase de ELE, in J.F. Barrio Barrio (coord.), Actas de las Jornadas de Formación del Profesorado en la Enseñanza de L2/ELE y la Literatura Española Contemporánea, Sofía: Ministerio de Educación de España y Universidad de Sofía "San Clemente de Ojrid", 185-204. http://www.educacion.es/exterior/bg/es/publicaciones/actas_sofia_3_junio_web.pdf